

GRIEVING PROCESS OF FRONTLINERS WITH COVID-19 FAMILY DEATH: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

The global COVID-19 pandemic has killed thousands and devastated survivors, friends, and families with 118,000 cases and 4,291 deaths in 114 countries made COVID-19 a pandemic on March 11, 2020. As of September 28, 231 million cases and 4.7 million fatalities have been reported globally (WHO, 2020). This study used narrative inquiry to focus on the grieving process of front-line nurses who have experienced a significant death loss during the COVID-19 pandemic and have persisted in their career in the face of adversity. Its purpose was to understand and describe the grieving process of front-line nurses after a significant death loss. Providing this affirmative narrative illuminated the career resilience that occurs following a death loss experience. Using psychosocial resilience as the conceptual model, the overarching research question that guided this study was: What are the narratives of bereaved front liners after the death of a family member due to COVID-19? What process of grieving may be identified from the findings? Participants included five front-line nurses from the Philippines and the United Arab Emirates. Participants shared their death loss experiences through semi-structured interviews and journaling. Face-to-face and virtual interviews were conducted. The data from this study was presented using narratives. The five participants in this study were represented by five composite characters who met monthly virtually. The findings revealed difficulties that bereaved front-liners faced, such as how their ties and relationship to the departed were not always recognized by public. Furthermore, distance from one's support networks and a lack of funds frequently created barriers to grieving and mourning. Most participants had more than one death loss, but they address concerns at the leading edge of their narrative. Additionally, the findings discovered stages of grieving process through their powerful stories. Finally, all participants shared how they were able to keep going with their chosen profession as a nurse after losing a loved one. This study adds to the growing body of literature on bereaved front-line nurses in healthcare.

Keywords: COVID-19, front line nurses, death, bereavement, grieving process

Introduction

The devastating effect of the COVID-19 epidemic has been recorded in countries worldwide, with significant death tolls and evidence that survivors, friends, and families have been severely impacted. COVID-19 was announced a pandemic on March 11, 2020, after 118,000 cases and 4,291 fatalities were recorded in 114 countries. As of September 28 (the most recent statistics available for this study), there have been 231 million cases worldwide, with 4.7 million deaths due to the infection (WHO, 2020).

Physicians, nurses, and allied health professionals are some of the 'unsung' heroes in the ongoing battle against COVID-19. Aside from long work hours in unpleasant and demanding environments, the loss of close relatives due to covid-19 added psychological stresses that could threaten their well-being, morale, and work effectiveness (Waleed et al., 2020). Medical frontline workers who have lost a loved one to COVID-19 are also at greater risk of developing substantial mental health problems, which manifest as symptoms such as stress, severe depression, loss of work motivation, sadness, and trauma (Jianbo et al., 2020).

Hospital visits were either prohibited or severely limited when the COVID-19 epidemic was in its early phases, and family members were frequently segregated from their family members admitted to hospitals (Azoulay et al., 2021). The family was no longer permitted to see the patient on their deathbed, which may have jeopardized their ability to participate in decision-making. Many doctors believed this condition was damaging to both patients and their families (Barnes et al., 2021). Communication with family members is significantly altered in this environment and predominantly relies on distance communication—most typically via telephone, but occasionally via video conferencing—possibly resulting in a deterioration in the quality of communication, content, and sense of support. Grieving family members are at a greater risk of developing symptoms that might negatively impact their quality of life after a death in the hospital, such as stress, despair, posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms, and complicated mourning. Surprisingly, witnessing terminal dyspnea and not even grieving a loved one have been linked to higher psychological distress among families (Barnes et al., 2015).

As a result, this paper hypothesized that the COVID-19 epidemic, as well as the preventive measures put in place in its wake, may have amplified these unpleasant experiences. Aside from these potentially difficult hospital experiences, past research has found that large-scale epidemics are linked to several simultaneous losses, including not only death but also alterations in societal expectations, end-of-life rituals, and grieving practices (Maryland, 2020). Individuals' inability to connect with the departed may hamper; as a result, thus raising the likelihood of complicated mourning and grief (Gesi et al., 2020).

After a loved one's needs are met when they pass away, relatives are claimed to manage and adjust better in grief, with higher psychological contentment and outcomes with end-of-life care. Open and honest communication from health and social care professionals about a family member's disease and declining health and the opportunity to make one final communication with their member of the family before they die are crucial part of one's grieving process. The pandemic's actual ramifications may substantially influence families' health and well-being, as well as their overall well-being after the loss of a loved one.

This narrative study aims to understand and describe front liners' experiences and possibly find out their process of grief after a significant loss due to COVID-19 in order to attend to their needs during this most difficult time. It will provide essential insights into how the family manages and adjusts throughout the crisis. It will help in understanding how to satisfy the needs and demands of families in the event of a pandemic, with significant therapeutic and

policy ramifications. Lessons learned may also be relevant in other situations where personal interactions are not feasible towards the end of one's life, such as when family members are abroad or when contagious illness epidemics arise.

In addition, given the lack of research in this subject, it is critical to learn from the current COVID-19 situation. More specifically, it is important to understand healthcare frontline workers' experience with loss during the pandemic to develop practices and contribute guidelines that will be helpful to support grieving families in times of crisis. In the setting of significant health crises, qualitative research is essential for shedding light on the subjective experience of bereaved family members, unearthing their thoughts and feelings, and improving our knowledge of their needs.

Although a loss is an unavoidable aspect of life, death and dying as a process can bring worry, sorrow, and misery, with people's reactions being directly linked to their personal views, sociological, philosophic factors, and culture (Peters et al., 2013). Six hundred sixty-eight thousand people have died in 216 nations due to the new Coronavirus, COVID-19, which began in Wuhan, China (WHO, 2020). As a result, discussions about death and dying have become regular in the news and among families. Still, people cannot say goodbye or carry out their grieving rituals. It complicates the process of embracing death/dying and adds to the psychological distress of people who have lost relatives or acquaintances.

Death and Society

Death was a constant feature in the nineteenth century. People of all ages commonly died at home rather than in hospitals. Furthermore, instead of funeral homes, the remains of the departed were frequently displayed and visited by others in houses. Much has altered over time due to medical advancements and increased lifespans. Civilization has evolved by normalizing activities such as letting strangers care for persons nearing death and family members employing funeral houses to manage the deceased's body. Death and dying have become a more remote aspect of our daily lives as a result of this transformation, in comparison to how life used to be.

Death in modern, advanced society may appear inhumane despite medical advancements. These unsavory details are not often widely publicized. Death and dying have historically been seen as sensitive or improper topics to mention in certain communities; therefore, these discussions are frequently avoided. According to some researchers, it appears as though certain people have blocked themselves off from death.

People fascinated by death can now learn more about the issue and share their ideas via numerous social media venues (Brubaker et al., 2013). Additionally, thanatology, defined as "study encompassing all elements of death, dying, and grief, including end-of-life care" (Borgstrom & Ellis, 2017, p. 93), has grown in popularity and recognition for many. Experts devote their work to these subjects (Chapple et al., 2017).

Methodology

Research Design. Qualitative research is frequently used to "illustrate and comprehend the complexities of human beings' lives and the world in which we live" (Jones et al., 2014, p. 11). Since this paper was studying a front liner's demographic, qualitative research enabled the researcher to obtain detailed accounts from participants described as grieving front liners. Qualitative research design was chosen for the study because it was in a real-world setting and "has a significant impact on the reader" (Miles et al., 2014).

According to Daniel and Harland (2017), qualitative research is "exploratory in nature and focuses on investigating stories and the engagement of individuals within a given social

situation. Numerous data of front liners are experiencing the death of a loved one throughout their professional duty during the COVID-19 pandemic, and this study provides an opportunity to share their stories. The purpose of this study was to have participants relate their death loss stories and experience while also highlighting their triumphs in overcoming this type of hardship.

The use of narrative inquiry will enable the exploration and comprehension of the actual experiences of grieving front-liners who faced a significant loss during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to studies, "acknowledgment of the interpersonal and participatory nature of human science research, the use of storytelling, and an emphasis on a meticulous accounting of the species are trademarks of understanding in narrative inquiry" (p. 25). By concentrating on respondents' first-hand views, narrative inquiry tries to comprehend the lived experiences of individuals, such as common people and those on the outskirts of society, and their pivotal role in establishing occurrences (Jones et al., 2014; Kim, 2016). This technique aids in "illuminating the hidden, invisible, and overlooked elements of meaning" (Schaafsma et al., 2011), which perfectly fits the study's respondents.

A characteristic feature of narrative inquiry is the researcher's narration of the respondents' tales. Narrative inquiry delves into "the social, cultural, and institutional stories that molded, articulated, and enacted persons' experiences—but in a way that starts and ends with the storied lives of people involved". As a result, researchers become involved in the study process via a "shared narrative production and reconstruction throughout the inquiry". As a result, the researcher bears a great deal of responsibility, and researchers should develop confidence with their respondents (Jones et al., 2014). As previously said, the researcher earned the trust of the participants by being candid about the research and the affiliation to this issue. The death experience of the researcher was shared during this journey including the researcher's hardships and triumphs. The openness regarding the researcher's involvement in this study enabled researcher to engage with the subjects and create a true, trusting rapport with the participants. This transparency was critical considering the study's sensitive and private subjects.

Participants. Purposive sampling was employed as a non-probability sample strategy to concentrate on a group of participants who share a common attribute - they were frontline responders during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Palinkas (2015), purposeful sampling entails discovering and recruiting individuals with a wealth of information about the subject under study. Purposive sampling's major purpose is to obtain samples that can rationally be representative of a particular section or section of a population. The investigators will market the project by individually contacting potential volunteers. Additionally, the researcher approached the individual by connections who served as frontline responders during the epidemic to see if they would be willing to join or provide potential participants' references. Participants were approached within one (1) week of the University Ethics Review Committee approving the study.

To recruit participants who would offer high-quality data (Morse, 2007), the researcher developed the following criteria for eligibility: (1) Participants must have experienced the significant death loss of a family member or a loved one during the COVID-19 pandemic, (2) Participants must be a nurse and front-liner working in a healthcare or social institution, and (3) willing to participate in the study.

Upon planning this study, the optimum number of participants were five and seven. The researcher intended to pick participants using the principle of maximum variance. Possible participants were invited to engage in this study if they matched all the study's eligibility criteria and willing to meet with me during the data gathering time. Participants then acknowledged their

availability and communicated with them the day and hour of meeting using the application Zoom, Botim, and Facebook Messenger.

Instrumentation. A semi-structured interview approach was used in the current study. It is deemed appropriate for several reasons. Firstly, semi-structured interviews are among the most utilized approaches within qualitative research (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). Secondly, semi-structured interviews have been commonly employed across various applied mental health-related qualitative studies (Brooks et al., 2017; Reid, et al., 2018). Finally, this approach enabled the research team to ask open-ended questions to allow participants to convey their thoughts, feelings, and experiences without being led or biased by the interviewer (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). This approach, therefore, is optimal for allowing participants space to expand upon personal or sensitive issues and/or provide important new information about the research topic that the interviewer was previously unaware of while also keeping the interview focused (Jamshed, 2014).

Data Analysis. Creswell (2013) proposed that analysis of data begins with "preparation and organization, followed by a coding process and consolidating the codes, and ultimately, representation of the data in graphs, charts, or a discussion" (p.180). To prepare for data analysis, the researcher transcribed the electronically recorded interview sessions and engaged in the subjects' diaries by reading them numerous times to become acquainted with their narratives. Following that, a theme story was conducted and the analysis on the data from this investigation.

According to Reissmann (2008), "in theme narrative analysis, the emphasis is on 'the told'—the occurrences and thoughts and feelings to which word refers (the speech's content)." (Ibid., p. 58). As a result, the emphasis was on the essence of the narratives rather than their structure. This method of analysis "honors individuals' tales as facts that can stand alone as pure descriptions of experience".

The researcher engaged in narrative coding using both inductive and deductive methodologies to "reflect the subjects' tales from a literary standpoint" (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2016, p. 138). According to Saldaa (2013), storytelling coding is "suitable for analyzing interpersonal and intrapersonal participant experiences and acts to better understand the human experience through the story, which is a genuine mode of knowing in and of itself. Utilization of inductive coding to derive codes from semi-structured interviews and diary activities were used. More precisely, employing in vivo codes or the keywords used by subjects (Creswell, 2013). When identifying items that frequently emerged throughout the literature review, the researcher employed deductive coding. Next, the data was consolidated which is the procedure by which the researcher selected and simplified the data (Miles et al., 2014). The information was frequently classified using a word or short phrase that encapsulated a thought (Jones et al., 2014; Saldaa, 2013) and arranged them into main conclusions using "important and essential information quotes" (Daniel & Harland, 2017, p. 113).

Participants were encouraged to cooperate throughout the research, operating under an interpretive paradigm. The interview transcripts and story codes was emailed to the participants and collaborated on developing the research findings. Researcher then used a composite narrative to convey the results in a future chapter. This paper was influenced by Patton and Catching's study, which emphasized the experiences by employing counter-storytelling through composite narratives. Counter-storytelling is anchored in Critical Race Theory and aims to tell the stories of underprivileged communities' groups of people whose stories are rarely shared. Although this study was not about race or racism, and grieving front liners are not labeled as marginalized communities, the researcher loved how the counter-storytelling method enables

persons who have been privileged to have their views and stories heard. Many policies and practices do not explicitly acknowledge grieving front liners, and the psychosocial resilience of bereaved front-liners is often disregarded in research papers. The researcher chose to employ the concept of counter-storytelling to question the dominant narrative, which emphasizes the difficulties faced by bereaved front liners, such as a deterioration in career and professional duties following a death loss.

Results

Figure 2. LIDAY's Loss and Grieving Process as identified by the participants.

Lability (Emotional)

The first theme, lability in terms of emotion, illustrated the clear differences in each nurse's psychological impact when a family died or endured great suffering (Lewis, 2017). The nurses' capacity to comprehend the death and express their grief will determine the intensity of the emotional reaction (Gibson et al., 2018). In this study, front-line nurses described the grieving process impacts their emotional response to the death loss. One participant verbalizes: "I was so out of breath that I had to feverishly run back and forth, and I went outside on my porch and just sat there gasping for air. As I bereaved."

Participants were asked, "How did you feel when you found out about her/his death?" How did it feel afterward? Front line nurses did express an intense feeling of unhappiness, agony, disbelief, and shock. Fatima said It was hard accepting the news. I did not believe it at; first, I was like in shock, and I couldn't breathe. Ria described similarly getting the information: It was a nightmare when it happened. I knew he was dying. We brought him to the emergency room by ambulance, and when we got there, it was like I didn't want to see what was happening. I am outside the hospital, walking in the hallway back and forth. I don't know what to do or what to think. I'm crying inconsolably. My emotions are killing me, and I can't concentrate.

Furthermore, when each person began to describe their experience, horrifying words of shock, sorrow, and disbelief came to light. According to Seta, "I think every one of us was just kind of in shock, and it felt like a terrible nightmare." Similar to Seta, all of the participants agreed that "It was heartbreaking. It didn't seem possible."

When a person's regular stream of thinking is disrupted by unwanted ideas or pictures connected to an experience, upsetting grieving symptoms such as fears, recurrent thoughts, or flashbacks occur (Simon, 2013). This supports the participant's statement, "I constantly reflect on death. I'm still tense and apprehensive because I know that the people, I care about could pass away at any moment. For example, considering my grandmother has been slowing down, I frequently wonder how much time I have left with her, even my sibling. As a result of my increased paranoia regarding his whereabouts and activities, I insist that he text me every time he leaves the house so that I can ensure his safety".

Although these labile emotions can be challenging to manage, they are typically seen as normal responses to distressing events, and the overwhelming experiences weaken and disappear over time (Shear, 2012). For some nurses, long-lasting emotions can interfere with work or sleep (e.g., "I hardly ever have a night without some form of a dream, it is somewhat disturbing"). Comprehending these strong emotional reactions may cause nurses to become disconnected or want to avoid seeing people (Gibson et al., 2018; Missouriidou, 2017; Wallbank & Robertson, 2013).

The participants also repeatedly used the word "surreal" to understand the news's reality. Surreal is "extremely weird or strange: exhibiting the characteristics of a dream" by Merriam Webster (2013). Front line nurses used descriptions like "stuck in reality," "feeling lost," "like zombies," "quite zoned out," and an "out of world sensation" to describe their first and following emotions. Similar to this, Corr, Nabe, and Corr (2009), thanatology specialists, anecdotally coined the term "psychological numbing" to describe this moment (p. 223). According to Charisse, she was "attempting to like just shut everything off tad bit just attempting to zone out." "It was just like some folks say it's like an out-of-world sensation, you're in the situation, but your thoughts are like stuck in time," she added.

The participants' emotional suffering liability from grieving is similar to elements of Worden's work's original phase- and task-based definitions of grieving (2009). Worden (2009) also indicated that people need to recognize the reality of the loss and move through the agony of grieving in the first two parts of his task-based approach to grieving. He claims that the bereavement process cannot be completed without experiencing the emotional sorrow of grief. The emotional anguish experienced as a result of loss is described as feelings of despair, rage, loneliness, and regret (Worden, 2009).

The study's findings are confirmed by recent literature, and adding nurse perspectives of loss—as opposed to quantitative measurements of sadness or difficult grief—adds to the body of information. Instead of using standardized, quantitative measurements for grieving, analyzing the nurses' perspectives enables a deeper comprehension of individual grief experiences.

Indignation

Responses to the narrative inquiry revealed indignation as a second theme when participants were asked and attempted to retrace the events after the loss.

Indignation is an essential component of the process of recovery. Even though it could seem to last forever, be open to experiencing your indignation. It will start to fade away, and you'll heal more quickly the more you truly experience it (Kessler, 2005, p. 12). Even though it is

a frequent sign of sadness (Archer, 1999), evidence suggests that not everyone experiences indignation (Bonanno & Keltner, 1997; Shuchter & Zisook, 1993).

People display outward frustration and ask why something happened. This period may be especially challenging when the loss is unexpected or blindsided. Resentment takes the form of a control-seeking behavior that enables us to temporarily take control of our surroundings to escape the feeling of becoming helpless. One response from the participant says, "She had been struggling with symptoms for a few weeks before she died. Due to the full capacity of the hospital where they were living, Shiela stayed home, where her condition worsened. She was brought to the hospital due to difficulty breathing and a high fever, but it was too late for the doctors to save her. This is the government's fault, says Myrna. If they are ready for this pandemic, my sister is still alive. This is their fault. Our healthcare system is not ready for this pandemic. That is why people are dying in their homes". Myrna's resentment is towards the government's unpreparedness to deal with this health crisis.

During certain periods of the normal mourning process, the grieving person may feel hurt, helpless, and resentful. It is typical for such turbulent feelings to come to the surface and be directed at someone or something. Finding someone to blame is only natural when sorrow rules the emotions. Indignation is a means to let off steam and express dissatisfaction over a defeat that doesn't make sense or feel fair. Even when one knows in their hearts that indignation is neither rational nor warranted, emotions are rarely rational. The truth of the situation starts to sink in once the person has stopped trying to deny that the loss has happened, which causes more perplexity, annoyance, and anguish. The body and mind start to turn away from the pain, presenting it as indignation instead. Indignation can be directed against inanimate objects, such as walls or trash cans, by hitting or stomping them. It may be directed against individuals, including friends, family members, and total strangers.

Occasionally, the grieving loved one who has passed away may be the target of the rage. Indignation frequently goes in cycles. When one feels bad for being furious, it just makes one's resentment grow. Some participants verbalized their feeling of anger toward a colleague. On Ria's statement, "I was simply attempting to process all that had occurred. That was the only way I knew how to accomplish it. And I don't want to be surrounded by others."

Similarly, Charisse verbalizes, "I remembered being so furious because I ride myself to work and all I have to deal with is this ridiculous flower pot, and I was so upset at everyone for whatever reason." And I brought this hatred around with me, offended by everything. My colleagues' attempts at sympathy were not what I wanted, and it was the odd type of stuff at the crucial moment, and I became increasingly annoyed. When I first returned to work, I recall feeling more enraged than usual since the world was so humiliating to me that I had to reintegrate my life and show that everything was okay".

However, as evidenced by their ongoing battle with loss, grieving as encountered by the front-line nurses are experiences bigger than just emotions and not just a simple outburst of these mentioned reactions. Resentment, envy, and rage are common responses to unwelcome information and may accompany this. At this point, people could struggle to manage, so providing them with a safe environment, time, and attention is critical.

Dealing

There comes the point in the grieving process when our emotions settle down, and we begin to gradually consider the truth of our current circumstances. With what is unfolding, indignation seems to be out of the question. Although sadness after a loved one's death can be

terribly isolating, it is a fairly normal mourning period. According to Zheng et al. (2018), dealing with grief and suffering following a death can be emotionally challenging, which may be why it needs to be addressed. Additionally, Kissane and Hooghe (2011) recommended that establishing interpersonal relationships is crucial in overcoming losses and that sharing grief generally promotes healing.

During the beginning stages of the pandemic, participants were left grieving and had to deal with the situation. Because of the lockdown's restrictions and limitations and, in some cases, their quarantines, front-line nurses were mostly sought out. They received support for their loss through telephone calls, video chats, or messages. Nevertheless, they could get adequate assistance from their social network despite the restrictions imposed.

Participants made it clear how helpful they considered it to have outside support during their time of need. When asked what she believes is beneficial after experiencing a loss, one participant (Ria) said, "Well, aside from being there for each other, you mean?" This participant's response eloquently demonstrated the crucial importance that supports from others plays. Other participants talked about how expressing their pain with others gave them some relief. Having a solid support system of sympathetic coworkers is crucial. For managing grief, the healthcare organization is seen as a valuable resource (Wenzel et al., 2011). Having comfortable and spontaneous interactions with colleagues at work can show assistance and a chance to talk about common experiences with loss. This can help front-line nurses who have been exposed to unfavorable circumstances during this pandemic to cope with their distress and loss. (Shorter & Stayt, 2010; Vega-Vega et al., 2019; Winning et al., 2018).

Dealing with the loss is not easy as perceived by the participants but sharing it with someone helps to make it much lighter than attempting to handle it alone.

I initially believed I couldn't overcome this, but fortunately, my mother and brothers were all around each other. Because doing it together kind of takes the edge off. I was fortunate to have support workers, so I didn't have to move alone. (Myrna)

They simply talk to you. Knowing how you are and informing you that they are still with you helps me deal with this profound loss. (Seta)

Just accept the help of others. Allow anyone to assist you, and you will notice the big impact on the weight you are carrying. It is what I did and helped me deal with this loss. Thanks to my roommate. (Ria)

Participants also emphasized that this support is occasionally unavailable, typically due to time constraints.

I haven't had the opportunity. My unit manager and colleagues have been busy. (Fatima)

Charisse, one of the participants, was straightforward about the kind of well-intended support that she considered hurtful.

Some people will try to assist you. Some people will essentially simply leave you. when they don't even bother to talk to you, etc., I'll just say, "Come on." Come on; everything will be OK. That simply makes me feel a little bit sad. (Charisse)

In determining support experiences, participants narrate the ability to reflect upon their experiences and recognize them as helpful or otherwise in dealing with the loss. It is unknown if it might affect their willingness to ask for assistance in the future.

The varying responses of the participants in the study showed how front-line nurses deal with grief in various ways, some of which may be more adaptable over time than others.

Admittance

Admittance is the next step in the participant's narrative of the grieving process. At this point, those who have lost a loved one may eventually admit their loss without a further battle. Grieving people are vulnerable and ready to embrace reality and their circumstances. A subdued resignation defines this period. It is not a joyful time. People could be a little reclusive and in need of some distance. The constant support and encouragement provided by therapists and other caregivers' mere presence are what people need most. Sometimes they might require treatment (James & Gilliland, 2005).

James and Gilliland (2005) identified three prevalent themes in people's responses to death in modern society: admittance, death-defying, and avoidance. According to Bottum (2007), acknowledging death fosters resilience and improves dealing with loss and grief since it gives a clear sense of reality. According to Worden (2002), anthropologists who have researched mourning in numerous civilizations have observed that grieving pathology appears to be less prevalent where there is a cultural process to acknowledge and deal with the effects of loss and grief than where there isn't one. The perspective of Kastenbaum, Doka, Beder, Scwab, and Farbero (2003), described by Bottum (2007) and corroborated by numerous research, is that grieving without a social outlet and process to deal with the effect is harmful to people's physical and emotional wellbeing.

Participants' reports of their experiences with loss revealed that they dealt with it by getting on with their lives and admitting the loss to some degree, by pushing themselves to forget about their grief. Remarkably, two people had said this. It is uncertain if this is a coincidence or if it symbolizes the mindset fostered by caregivers or supporters.

Usually, you just have to admit it, move on with your life, and do so. They would still want you to live your life and pursue your own goals if they were still alive. (Ria)

I must continue living my own life. I must therefore stop feeling defeated about the loss. I have to accept the loss, and I should attempt to remain optimistic and go on with my life. It motivates me and such. To continue living my own life. (Myrna)

Others who took part in the interview mentioned that they eventually tried to put their grief in the past by acting on it. One participant (Fatima) described focusing on her goals and leaving the grief behind helped her to accomplish her career goals. Others talked about how being busy and participating in social activities assisted them in getting over their loss. Most participants viewed this phase of moving on and admittance of the loss as a positive experience.

You forget about what happened when you're with other people. And that saved you from worrying about your family or anything at all. Because other people were around, you forgot about your loss and everything, which was helpful. And it benefited me. Yes. You see, you just focused on your goals and brushed aside what had happened. (Ria)

This emphasizes how important it is to maintain a level of normalcy after a loss. Participants may have resumed prior hobbies after admitting the loss occurred and may have developed new interests in order to pass the time. In any case, it seems that having the freedom to "be oneself" after a loss was a great experience. This feeling of comfort may stem from the realization that, in some ways, even without their loved one, they, as individuals, and the reality around them, continue to thrive recognizably and predictably.

Yearning

According to O'Connor and Sussman (2014), "Yearning is a psychological response frequently encountered in loss-related circumstances, centered on a yearning for a former loved

one, place, or thing. There are many different things and people that you might yearn for. If something is substantial enough to cause grief, it is undoubtedly significant enough to yearn for.

In this period, some participants are vividly aware of the gaping hole the loss has left in their lives. One participant commented, "I wish my father is still alive. I always remember him saying that I can do whatever I dreamed of with perseverance and hard work. I miss him, especially on my birthday".

I miss my mom, and on every important occasion, I always remember her. It doesn't mean I am helpless or unable to cope. On the contrary, recollections of my mom have evolved into my coping technique. This could be seen as another method for me to use our memories to assist me in meeting my current needs.

Subsequent research has revealed that yearning is a typical grief feeling. According to researchers, yearning increased until about four months after a loss, when it normally began to drop (Maciejewski et al., 2007).

Grieving process studies and literature frequently categorize emotions as positive or negative, which can help describe, evaluate, categorize, and contrast but may be misleading for our daily lives. Instead, we find it helpful to think of most feelings as being on a continuum that can be either good or unpleasant, depending on who is feeling the emotion, how they are handling it, and how much it affects them.

The possible negative

Bowlby and Parkes suggested that if an individual cannot move past the "yearning and seeking process," they will become trapped attempting to fill the space of their loss. Complicated grief researchers note that complicated grief is "described by a frequent and severe yearning for the deceased." The yearning was perhaps the most frequently endorsed "negative" feeling in the 2007 study mentioned above.

This should serve as a reminder that individuals frequently suffer unpleasant and difficult yearning in the initial stages of mourning and that occasionally people experience extremely unbearable yearning that persists and adversely impacts their ability to function daily.

The potential positive

On the other hand, I think many people would assert that they don't think their yearning is wholly unfavorable. According to several grief specialists, yearning can offer bittersweet pleasant feelings and solace for those mourning by drawing them closer to their loved one's memories.

Even though it differs slightly from yearning, research on nostalgia has found that it can occasionally be employed in constructive ways. One research finding. "A group from Southampton discovered that nostalgia is a relatively common experience, with 172 participants reporting experiencing it at least three or four times per week for 42% of them and at least three or four times per week for 80% of them. The discovery that negatives affect is one of the most frequent causes of nostalgia interests us the most. This shows that to combat unpleasant feelings like worry and stress in the present, we are likely to recall happy occasions in the past.

Additionally, their findings support the theory that nostalgia can foster good impact, strengthen social ties, and boost self-esteem. Therefore, thinking back on old relationships can help improve confidence in one's capacity to engage, open up, and connect with others in social situations that are likely to cause anxiety or fear.

Nostalgia and yearning have a lot of characteristics. I think it's possible to assume that (1) yearning and nostalgia are both employed as coping mechanisms, or (2) mourning individuals may mistakenly think they're experiencing yearning when they're using nostalgia to deal with unpleasant grief emotions.

Several participants discussed the significance that remembering and forgetting a loved one might play. The complexity of the undertaking was beautifully expressed in the following statement. One participant (Ria) responded when asked what advice she would offer to someone that has recently lost a loved one.

I will tell you to forget. And, to ALWAYS remember. A bit of both. (Ria)

Understanding that yearning is a widespread experience is crucial when comprehending it. It's crucial to realize that attitudes toward yearning could initially be conflicted or evolve with time. Since grief is about mourning the loss of something, yearning and many other grief-related responses are a mixture of joy and sorrow, good and awful.

Discussion

This research investigates the grieving front-line nurse's experiences after the death of a loved one due to COVID-19. Such research from more heavily affected areas is critical for providing insight into the experience of unpleasant grief and loss during the COVID19 pandemic. The inability of local authorities and the healthcare system to prevent the outbreak and handle the health crisis (Bosa et al., 2021) may have affected those who had lost a loved one.

All through the process that led to losing their loved ones, participants' experiences were marked by uncertainty. Even among health practitioners, in the early onset of the pandemic, there was chaos about identifying a COVID-19 case, which manifestations to look for, and the true risk of the virus spreading to the public. Furthermore, nursing staff holding their phones close to the bed were the only means for participants to talk with their loved ones in the hospital. This example of frontline health care workers' respect and concern is likely to have aided grieving families in making sense of their loss (Wakam et al., 2020). Communication is imperative at the end-of-life care, and health care professionals must be trained to provide this type of assistance, which is crucial for both patient populations preparing for their death and their friends and family (Cipolletta & Reggiani, 2021; Ersek et al., 2021).

The COVID-19 grieving front-line nurses included in this research had all recently experienced a loss (i.e., within the last 18 months). They felt sorrow, despair, and shock, typical of the initial quarters of mourning a painful loss (Ross et al., 2018). Loss during the COVID19 pandemic can impede meaning-making for grief-stricken people (Eisma & Tamminga, 2020): staying at home, financial hardship, and constant worry regarding personal or others' health are all attributable to mourners' inability to engage in essential activities such as acquiring help and assistance and participating to life changes (Neimeyer & Burke, 2017), that are critical for meaning-making and posttraumatic improvement (Milman et al., 2017; Neimeyer, 2019).

Among all the participants, those who struggled more to give meaning to their loss were those mourners who believed their loved ones departed prematurely or unjustly. They felt angry toward professionals for not having avoided a preventable death (Ahmadi & Ramezani, 2020) and blamed administrations for making sense of their loss (Carr et al., 2020; Neimeyer, 2001) while denying the emotions linked to the loved one's death. With the COVID-19 pandemic being a global-scale event, mourners are constantly reminded of the circumstances of their loved ones' deaths. For those struggling to accept their loss, it could become tempting to concentrate all their energies on associating in groups and to pour their anger into the pursuit of justice rather than

begin accepting the loss. The disappointment toward inadequate administrations, which was only briefly described in studies reporting practitioners' experiences (Alizadeh et al., 2020; Dhairyawan, 2021), was observed consistently throughout the experiences of several participants and took the form of open conflict with the governance. This attitude could be attributed to how the population relates to politics (Capano, 2020) and often mistrusts healthcare services (Cipolletta & Reggiani, 2021). It is a factor that should be considered for further studies: its presence should be verified in different Western cultural contexts because this study shows how it could significantly affect the ability to adapt to the pandemic scenario and the loss.

Conclusion

When the current study was written, other authors had only foreseen potential grieving aftermath based on prior experience with other painful losses (Eisma et al., 2020; Masiero et al., 2020; Wallace et al., 2020, Boelen et al., 2020). What hasn't been discovered or expected in the literature about COVID-19 deaths is mourners' need to witness and lambast an unfair circumstance as well as the more operational strong desire to alert others and prevent a re-occurrence of such a circumstance, the primary coping strategies highlighted by the current study.

Grievers' reported issues or outright opposition toward mental health services may have treatment repercussions. Experts who reach COVID19 grieving families should be cognizant that their clients may be extremely dissatisfied with services, and as an outcome, their compliance may already be uncertain (Gravante & Poma, 2021; Testoni et al., 2021). Acknowledging this viewpoint, rather than opposing it, may aid in developing a cooperative process in which the suffering individual and the professional collaborate for a shared goal. This remedy is consistent with that discovered by those participants who utilized their own significant experience as a pivotal moment to seek a shift in focus from economic advantages to citizen support, obligation, and mutual recognition: they emphasized the importance of shifting to a different philosophy in which the individual, instead of the economy, is the main focus (Cipolletta & Ortu, 2021).

As Stroebe and Schut (2020) pointed out, there is still a slight factor to consider of beneficial or corrective procedures for potential grieving process alleviation in COVID19 mourners. Finding a silver lining is critical to accessing meaning restoration (Holland, Currier, & Neimeyer, 2006). Mourners felt relieved when they realized they were sharing their grief with many other individuals. Shared social grief may be a pivotal bind for the ability to comprehend loss, and it may be an excellent starting point for healthcare professionals looking to foster meaning-making. The current study's findings provide a sound foundation for further investigation of the evaluation process and its connections with loss acclimation in pandemic situations.

Undoubtedly, this research study is a significant first step in exploring the lived experiences of five front nurse liners with COVID-19 family death. There isn't much information available on this grieving experience in the population subset of front liners. Understanding human grief is crucial for nursing educators, university administrators, and nursing students. These participants have revealed through their powerful narratives that their loss is real and that they are trying to continue to be resilient in their careers despite these losses.

This narrative inquiry offers implications for practice to better support and understands bereaved nurse front liners. I present three recommendations for nursing professors, university administrators, and nursing students or future nurses based on the knowledge I have learned from this narrative inquiry to enhance the experiences of grieving students or future nurses.

Educational programs that teach effective coping strategies may be useful. Tailor-made grief and bereavement care program for front-line nurses would help them understand their emotions and better cope with death and dying. Various methods of coping, such as the expression of humor or the formation of a grief team to promote a supportive, nurturing environment, may also be helpful (Borsche 2007). A care philosophy for front-line nurses should be developed so that all health care professionals are consistent in their care planning and avoid disagreements. Regular group sharing sessions could be held to help nurses to support one another. Further research could be carried out using a longitudinal approach to better understand the cumulative loss effect on nurses from the death of patients.